

Wheat Yield Estimation/Prediction Using Multi-Temporal SPOT VGT NDVI Satellite Imagery in Pakistan

By

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of remote sensing data in wheat crop yield estimation and prediction in the Lodhran district of Punjab using SPOT VGT data. In particular, this investigation evaluates the usefulness of SPOT VGT data for early warning system and timely yield estimation of the wheat crop in Punjab. Traditionally, the monitoring of crop growth and yield forecasts are made on the basis of samples by field visits or written inquiries. The main objective of this study was to establish a relationship between SPOT VGT NDVI and yield on regional (District) level in Pakistan and to develop a methodology which can provide reliable yield estimates for wheat quickly and efficiently. The NDVI curve shows that the start of season (SOS) is around 3rd decade of December following two consecutive biweekly periods with positive NDVI increments. This could be seen as the 'steepening' of the growth curve when photosynthetic activity is first increasing. Conversely, end of season (EOS) was estimated around 3rd decade of April and 1st decade of May, as a decrease of NDVI values, this could be seen as the flattening of the curve' when photosynthetic activity has decreased substantially. When sequential NDVI observations are taken frequently over a season, seasonal profiles are developed that show the progression of crop canopy emergence, maturation and senescence, which reflect crop performance and are related to crop yields. To find any relationship between yield and NDVI summation of NDVI growth profiles was examined for assessing seasonal growth profiles. Summations of the NDVI growth profile were included to detect how early accurate yield estimates could be made. This study shows that NDVI seasonal growth profiles can provide good estimates of yield at the end of the growing season and during the later part of the growing season, prior to harvest, at the regional scale. SPOT VGT ten daily synthesis composite imagery currently provides the best source of regular and historical data at low cost, making it ideal for satellite imagery users. However, higher resolution imagery would provide more accuracy with respect to specific wheat producing areas.

Introduction:

In agriculture, monitoring of crop growth and development, and early estimates of the final productions to be expected are of general interest. Forecasting crop yield well before harvest is crucial. This enables planners and decision makers to predict how much to import in case of shortfall or optionally, to export in case of surplus. Since yield influences prices and subsidization it is also important on the farming level to reliably estimate its expected value as early as possible during the growing season. This enables the farmer to optimize return through optimized fertilizer/pesticide application or irrigation. In addition, realistic and timely estimates of yield expectation form the basis for monetary decisions in fields such as credit business and the stock exchange. Therefore, monitoring of crop development and crop growth, and early prediction are generally important. Yield

estimation is an important topic in agro-economic planning. It is generally carried out by agricultural and statistical state authorities to optimize price and storage policy on different governmental levels.

Traditional Methods:

Traditionally, the monitoring of crop growth and yield forecasts are made on the basis of samples by field visits or written inquiries. The traditional approach for crop estimation employs sample surveys for estimating crop acreages and sample surveys based on crop cutting experiments for

Fig1: Historical Wheat yield and Production in Lodhran District

estimating crop yield. The crop production estimates are obtained by taking the product of crop acreage and the corresponding crop yield. The yield surveys are fairly extensive with plot yield data collected under a complex sampling design that is based on random sampling design. A plot of specified dimensions within a field is selected for harvesting to determine the crop yield. The sample units are randomly selected.

Problems encountered concern subjectivity in responses, respondent differences and non-response. On national scale, the processing of these sample data is an expensive and time-consuming procedure. In general, there is a need for an objective, standardized and possibly cheaper and faster methodology for crop growth monitoring and yield forecasts.

Wheat is a major food crop cultivated in Pakistan mainly in the Provinces of Punjab and Sindh (Indus River Valley). Figure 2 shows the major Wheat producing districts in Pakistan.

Fig2: Major Wheat Producing Districts in Pakistan and Location of Lodhran District

Remote Sensing an Alternate:

Traditional methods of predicting crop yields throughout the growing season include models that assimilate climate, soils and other environmental data as response functions to describe development, photosynthesis, evapotranspiration and yield for a specific crop (Wiegand and Richardson 1990). Though based on strong physiological and physical concepts, these models are poor predictors when spatial variability in soils, stresses or management practices are present (Wiegand 1984, Wiegand and Richardson 1990). However, remote sensing of crop canopies has been promoted as a potentially valuable tool for agricultural monitoring because of its synoptic coverage and ability to 'see' in many spectral wavelengths (Hinzman *et al.* 1986, Quarmby *et al.* 1993). Numerous studies have recognized that plant development, stress and yield capabilities are expressed in the spectral reflectance from crop canopies and could be quantified using spectral vegetation indices (Jackson *et al.* 1986, Malingreau 1989, Weigand and Richardson 1990). Vegetation indices (VI), such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), are typically a sum, difference or ratio of two or more spectral wavelengths. They are highly correlated with photosynthetic activity in non-wilted plant foliage and are good predictors of plant canopy biomass, vigor or stress (Tucker 1979).

Vegetation monitoring using the red and near infrared SPOT VGT channels has been one of the most widely used indices. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) correlates closely with green biomass and the leaf area index. Despite the spatial resolution of 1 km at nadir, there are many scientific publications documenting the usefulness of SPOT VGT data as a means of monitoring vegetation conditions on a near real-time basis (Philipson and Teng, 1988; Bullock, 1992; Quarmby *et al.*, 1993).

Objectives and Research Question:

Many studies on the relationship between remote sensing data and crop yield have been done either on research involving very small areas with very high degree of control of many parameters affecting crop growth and production.

The main objective of this study was to establish a relationship between SPOT VGT NDVI and yield on regional (District) level in Pakistan and to develop a methodology which can provide reliable yield estimates for wheat quickly and efficiently.

The only research question tried to answer in this study was,

What is the relationship between SPOT VGT NDVI and wheat yield in Pakistan at district level?

Methods and Materials:

The district chosen for this study was Lodhran which lies in the south of Punjab province and one of the districts in Pakistan with extreme agriculture and big producer of the wheat. The average length of growing season of wheat in this area 135 days. Average Precipitation in wheat season is 09 mm. Since most of this area shows dry land conditions as shown in average metrological graph for the year, so very extensive canal irrigation network is available in the district. Fig 4 shows the location and extensive canal network of Lodhran district in Punjab.

Wheat yield data were collected from the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock (MinFAL) of Pakistan for the years 1990–2006.

SPOT VGT NDVI (10 days synthesis) data for this study was provided by SUPARCO's Space Applications Research Center (SPARCENT), Islamabad from April 1998 to April 2007.

Fig3: Five Year Average Max Temp and Average Rainfall in Lodhran District

Fig4: Lodhran District and Neighboring Districts

NDVI Growth Profile:

The NDVI seasonal growth profile was exploited according to several procedures. First of all mean NDVI of Lodhran district for the last five years average from 2002 to 2006 was plotted against the months in wheat growing season (From 1st Decade of November to 3rd Decade of May)

The green curve in the fig 05 shows an apparent growing season (AGS) was defined because growing season duration and date of initiation fluctuates from year to year with weather patterns (Groten 1993), however this averaged mean give us very good and accurate understating about the growing season, as we can derive Start of Season (SOS), End of Season (EOS) and average peak values for the whole growing season of wheat in Lodhran District.

The NDVI curve in fig 05 shows that the start of season (SOS) is around 3rd decade of December following two consecutive biweekly periods with positive NDVI increments. This could be seen as the 'steepening' of the growth curve when photosynthetic activity is first increasing. Conversely, end of season (EOS) was estimated around 3rd decade of April and 1st decade of May, as a

decrease of NDVI values, this could be seen as the flattening of the curve' when photosynthetic activity has decreased substantially.

The red curve in the fig 05 shows the mean NDVI values of growing season in 2006-07 of wheat in Lodhran. It is evident that in the start of season NDVI value was a bit higher than the 5 year average value of the same decade i.e 3rd decade of December 2006 and then the curve follows the 5 year average curve religiously until 3rd decade of January 2007. After that curve starts increasing than that of the 5 year average and attains its maximum value in 2nd decade of March 2007, which again is higher than that of the last five years. These higher NDVI values can be explained by the higher rainfall in the months of January and February 2007 in the study area.

Fig5: Average NDVI for Last Five Years i.e. 2001-02 to 2005-06 as Compared with Average NDVI for Year 2006-07 in Lodhran District

Early Warning Indicators:

Comparison in the NDVI curves of five year average with the present season as shown in fig 06 can be used to issue early warnings about crop health and expected yields of the crop both to the farmers and planners. In this case we can see that the curve for 2007 is higher than that of 5 year average explained by the higher rainfall, so we can expect good or higher yield for the year 2007 in Lodhran district.

Using the same approach, difference image was calculated for the 2006-07 season from last 5 year average. Fig?? shows the difference image, it delineate areas where the crop was better, worse or average as compared with the last 5 years average. The maps of this kind can be used as early warning bulletins.

Fig6: Difference Image of Average NDVI from 21 Dec to 20 Mar for Last Five Years and Average NDVI from 21 Dec to 20 Mar for Year 2006-07 in Lodhran District

Correlation Matrix:

When sequential NDVI observations are taken frequently over a season, seasonal profiles are developed that show the progression of crop canopy emergence, maturation and senescence, which reflect crop performance and are related to crop yields. To find any relationship between yield and NDVI summation of NDVI growth profiles was examined for assessing seasonal growth profiles. Summations of the NDVI growth profile were included to detect how early accurate yield estimates could be made. Summation of NDVI over select dates within a growing season was also done for examining NDVI growth profiles. We considered three summation periods around the time of maximum NDVI that encompass a 'critical period' in grain production that approximates flowering through maturity in wheat (Benedetti and Rossini 1993, Doraiswamy and Cook 1995). The three summation periods

were as follows: sum 21 December–20 February, sum 21 December–28 (Last day) February and sum 21 December–10 March. Another procedure investigated the relationship of wheat yield and average of three max NDVI values throughout the growing season and max NDVI value of each growing season. These all parameters were collected for the SPOT NDVI data from December 1998 to March 2006, i.e. eight growing seasons and a correlation matrix was developed to see if any relationship lies among the wheat yield and these five phenological parameters.

	Average Yield in Kg/Ha	NDVI SUM 21Dec - 20 Feb	NDVI SUM 21Dec - 28 Feb	NDVI SUM 21Dec - 10 Mar	Average NDVI 3Max	NDVI Max
Average Yield in Kg/Ha	1	0.714	0.644	0.493	-0.425	0.456
NDVI SUM 21Dec - 20 Feb	0.714	1	0.992	0.534	0.115	0.197
NDVI SUM 21Dec - 28 Feb	0.644	0.992	1	0.492	0.217	0.29
NDVI SUM 21Dec - 10 Mar	0.493	0.534	0.492	1	-0.304	-0.21
Average NDVI 3Max	-0.425	0.115	0.217	-0.304	1	0.929
NDVI Max	-0.456	0.197	0.29	-0.21	0.929	1

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Matrix, figures in Red show Significant Correlation

Results and discussions:

Integration of seasonal NDVI profiles summation of the seasonal NDVI growth profile relationships with yield considered to be significant estimators of yield. Max NDVI and average of three Max NDVI of each season show almost no (Negative) trends or association with final yield. However summations of critical periods sum 21 December–20 February, sum 21 December–28 (Last day) February and sum 21 December–10 March showed strong correlation, with strongest correlation for the summation period of sum 21 December–20 February as shown in table 1. The significance of the yield for these NDVI parameters increased as the season progressed, however they did not become significant until mid of February was reached as shown in table 1. For these parameters, interaction terms were included in the final model and it gives us very simple model for the prediction of wheat yield in Pakistan and this model states that

$$\text{Wheat Yield} = f(\text{sum of NDVI 21 December–20 February})$$

To calculate wheat yield in Lodhran district NDVI SUM 21 Dec – 20 Feb for eight wheat seasons from 1998-99 to 2005-06 was plotted against the wheat

yield of these years for the whole district. This regression gave us the equation which was used to forecast the wheat yield of the 2006-07 seasons in Lodhran district of Punjab.

SPOT VGT NDVI seasonal growth profiles were found effective at representing wheat grain yields in Lodhran district. SPOT VGT NDVI growth profiles most likely relate to seasonal biomass production. Those seasons with higher biomass result in higher wheat yields that are represented by larger areas under the seasonal growth profile or larger summations over the season. This effect can be seen in the predicted slope of the wheat yield integrated NDVI scatter plots in regression of SUM NDVI with yield of the area under study.

It was found that reported and predicted yields area under study showed moderate to strong positive relationships with sum of NDVI. Seasonal biomass–NDVI relationships have been observed in many studies (Benedetti and Rossini 1993, Quarmby *et al.* 1993, Thoma 1998). For this study, 'high biomass years' are typically years of higher grain production, presumably because of favorable growing conditions. For example, precipitation in 2000 and 2003 was abundant throughout the growing season and these were also years of higher than average yield in Lodhran district.

Fig7: Wheat yield in Lodhran from 1998-99 season to 2005-06 with adjusted $R^2 = 0.5329$ and predicted Yield= $1.886 (\text{NDVI SUM 21 Dec-20 Feb}) + 1272.1$

Maximum NDVI and Average of three maximum NDVI growth profiles show no relationship with wheat yield and sum of NDVI for different periods of season when crop achieve its 80% of greenness are strongly related to final grain yield. Therefore, while early-season monitoring might be useful for indicating whether crops have higher biomass than in a typical year, which could be a precursor to a high yield year, subsequent events such as drought, heat stress, insect infestation, disease or lodging that occur later in the season when grain is forming are unpredictable. Critical periods examined on or around the time of maximum NDVI show a significant relationship with wheat yields therefore crops must be monitored and modeled carefully during the time when crop has achieved its 80% of greenness to the peak of NDVI profile, which is from last decade of February to the Mid of March to make accurate pre-harvest wheat yield estimates.

Fig8: Wheat yield Forecast for the year 2006-07 in Lodhran

Conclusions:

This study shows that NDVI seasonal growth profiles can provide good estimates of yield at the end of the growing season and during the later part of the growing season, prior to harvest, at the regional scale. Wheat yield estimates made at the end of the growing season might allow Crop Reporting

Fig9: Wheat yield Forecast for the Year 2006-07 in Lodhran in Comparison with Previous Years

Service (CRS) to improve the accuracy of regional yield statistics. SPOT VGT ten daily synthesis composite imagery currently provides the best source of regular and historical data at low cost, making it ideal for satellite imagery users. However, higher resolution imagery would provide more accuracy with respect to specific wheat producing areas.

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